

Introduction

If you attended the **New Horizon conference** you already know: **our commitment to Diamond OA is stronger than ever**. As we enter **the final year of the program**, our future is still being shaped and we hope to continue working on this **beyond 2026**. Behind the scenes, we are working on the **redesign of the website** and a new range initiatives. Take a look at [our agenda](#) to see what's coming next.

The Diamond OA Expertise Centre Team ([Bregt](#), [Erica](#), [Juliana](#), [Femke](#), [Stefano](#), [Maria](#))

News and Resources

Missed the New Horizons Conference? Catch up now!

Last February, together with our **Diamond OA ambassadors**, we organized the **New Horizon Conference in Nijmegen**. With over 100 participants and inspiring discussions, it was a true success. Dive into our **highlights** or watch the **recordings**.

A major boost for scholarly infrastructures thanks to openscience.nl

With 45 projects and 29.5 million euros in funding, Netherlands is at the forefront of making "open science the norm". Few projects we would like to highlight are [Infrastructures for Diamond OA in the Netherlands](#), [Next-generation publishing: Advancing the publish-review-curate model](#), National OA Books platform, [Scaling small in NL](#), [DURE](#), [BROCCOLI](#) and the UKB Publishing Browser.

Upgrade your publishing services with expert-led training!

The European Capacity Hub has developed five practical course modules based on the Diamond OA Standard—covering funding, editorial management, legal and ethical issues, and technical aspects. Ready to get started? Access the free EDCH Training Platform now!

Discover Dutch Diamond OA at a glance via this interactive tool

Take a quick interactive tour of Dutch journals and, if you're still exploring, check out the vibrant ecosystem of student journals too.

We are taking part of the new European project on Diamond OA

Together with other national capacity centers, the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) and other partners we are collaborating on the project [AEGIS-OA Activate European Guidance and Incentives for Sustainable Open Access publishing](#). This ambitious project aims at adapting the Diamond OA Standard for book publishing, next to improving the existing services of [EDCH](#)).

In the Spotlight

- The Joys, challenges and Insights gained from launching an (Diamond) OA journal, by Mette Birkedal Bruun University of Copenhagen, event organized by Open Science Community Rotterdam.
- MathOA has flipped two journals to Diamond OA and launched two new Diamond OA journals.
- Netherlands University Presses: moving towards diamond open access
- Diamond is the new Green—Why

- Diamond Open Access Needs Institutions, Not Heroes
- NWO grant awarded to the Netherlands University Presses
- CERN will host the publish-review-curate Diamond OA platform (Open Research Europe)

Green Open Access is not a sustainable long-term model for scientific publishing

- Follow the money article “Uitgevers maken melkkoe van ‘gratis’ toegang tot wetenschap” (Dutch only)

Agenda

- May 19 [Pathways towards an otherwise science: Mapping priorities and inspiring alternatives](#), Amsterdam
- More events can be found on [our website](#) and on [EDHC site](#).
- April, May [This is how we do it event series](#)
- June 3, [Openjournals network and users day 2026](#)
- May 19th, [SURF research day 2026](#)

You can find more information on Diamond OA, resources and events on our [website](#). Subscribe to our newsletter [here](#) and follow us on [LinkedIn](#). Should you have any questions, comments and/or suggestions, feel free to reach out via email [here](#). If you have Diamond OA related events to advertise in the newsletter or online, please [let us know](#).

LinkedIn

Website

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